

FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN THE MANAGEMENT AND IMPLEMENTATION OF PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP PROJECTS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12705314>

In France, efforts to develop road transport infrastructure through public-private partnerships began to appear 50 years ago in concession contracts. Over the next ten years, the total length of highways increased 8 times, and the share of roads built based on concession contracts made up 67% of the total size of roads. France has more than 10,000 km of roads, and more than 70% of them have been completed under concession contracts. In France, introducing the concept of "competitive dialogue" in 2004 is the key to PPPs' success. This concept is based on the fact that both private investors and state participants are among the participants in the implementation of large investment projects, and a solution that interests both of them has started to be heard for this project. In addition, the European Court of Justice has also adjusted the existing system to support free trade and competition, which has led to a decrease in the monopoly of state-owned enterprises.

In France, there are different forms of public-private partnership partnership: contractual and institutional. Of the PPP contract, a form is a concession contract to the object according to affairs and services, performs the right different to the parties is given Historically, infrastructure objects in financing state and private partners of the capital ratio of the first share growth in favour of has changed. This while own, in turn, big PPP projects demand significant funds with increased enable. The institutional form is this state and private partners by shared economy host the subject organize reach is calculated.

World in 2008 economic crisis, one-row investments stopped; however, that's it regardless of major French banking institutions large projects in financing risks own responsibilities received in the case in financing continue did From this In addition, the French Senate PPP mechanism more formation and attractive to for different suggestions with came out State by the PPP contract of support such measures to the line tax benefits, bank preferential loans and minimum bureaucratic procedures example by doing we get an the world from experience again one this Great in Britain dry completed M- 6 toll road is considered and this in British history the most successful from projects is

one The length of the toll highway is 43 km does in this project private partner as attended enterprise in Australia from the register past it was a foreign company. The road was from 2001 to 2003 term between three and less has been term during dry will be finished. The agreement, according to management and service terms, private partner for 2054 was of the project common worth 900 million pounds organize did Account to books according to the project work 15 years since its inception past for the benefit reach is necessary, that is, this is for 2018-2019 will come.

Great In Britain, successful PPPs are not only new in projects our observation is possible but exists the project through PPP again start through this project estimate £ 4.5m to £ 6.2m increased witness to be can This project is the River Thames building a tunnel under it graduation, 67km long of the road reconstruction to do and from the 220km long M-25 road to use containing. It is public-private 30 years of partnership in the form of a concession for a period contract signed. Estimate again seeing exit in the process is available to project perfected and to him various modifications input estimated value through to increase achieved.

Excellent 20 years in Britain concept of PFI during works, this concept is all procedures, financing attraction to do according to schemes, done increased projects, standard documents incarnate did document is the form Until then, to the PPP comfortable a must conditions create for this to PFI one how many times changes entered and again seeing released, and this through for the private sector conditions in the country economic to the situation suitable respectively by changing the bride came. Today's to the day laughing, the concept again seeing released and new conception duties set received To this according to tasks of the following consists of: addition debt funds attraction reach for comfortable conditions creation, investment environment development, institutional investors scope expansion, new contracts make up through risks reduce From a new concept intended prominent task project expenses efficiency increase, financing from sources use opportunities expansion, risk and benefit between balance from providing consists of

Another one from large PPP projects one Great Britain and France connecting iron is the way. It is a 108km long tunnel in the English Channel, costing 46.5 million pounds. This technically complicated project is considered, and from his intended goal, two states between contact is a simplification. Two countries between of the population daily migration according to all calculations counting when developed, the project successful that found However project from being

done then, of investments profitability 2 times more than expected less being came out and to this reason while later on different airlines and from ferry companies offer done cheap prices reason were.

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